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TUMORS OF THE FEMALE REPRODUCTIVE SYSTEM DURING DIABETES MELLITUS

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Relevance. *The article discusses various pathophysiological conditions and processes leading to the development of tumor diseases in diabetes mellitus. These include obesity, hyperglycemia, hyperinsulinemia, inflammation, and oxidative stress. Data from epidemiological studies are presented in which it was found that diabetes mellitus (both type 1 and type 2) increases the relative risk of developing tumors of the female reproductive system, such as ovarian and endometrial cancer, while for cervical cancer, vaginal cancer and vulvar cancer, such a relationship has not been clearly identified.*

Keywords: *diabetes; endometrial tumors; ovarian tumors; signaling pathways; neoplasm proteins.*

ОПУХОЛИ ЖЕНСКОЙ РЕПРОДУКТИВНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ПРИ САХАРНОМ ДИАБЕТЕ

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Актуальность. В статье рассматриваются различные патофизиологические состояния и процессы, приводящие к развитию опухолевых заболеваний при сахарном диабете. К ним относятся ожирение, гипергликемия, гиперинсулинемия, воспаление и окислительный стресс. Представлены данные эпидемиологических исследований, в которых установлено, что сахарный диабет (как 1-го, так и 2-го типа) повышает относительный риск развития опухолей женской репродуктивной системы, таких как рак яичников и эндометрия, тогда как при раке шейки матки, раке влагалища и при раке вульвы такая взаимосвязь четко не выявлена.

Ключевые слова: диабет; опухоли эндометрия; опухоли яичников; сигнальные пути; белки новообразований.

Introduction. The assumption that there is a relationship between diabetes mellitus (DM) and malignant neoplasms was made more than 100 years ago [1]. The risk of developing cancer increases with both type 1 (DM1) and type 2 (DM2) diabetes [2]. Among all causes of death in patients with diabetes, cancer ranks second after cardiovascular diseases [3]. It should also be noted that approximately 8–18% of cancer patients suffer from diabetes [4]. Meta-analyses and large population-based studies have shown that diabetes is associated with an increased risk of mortality in cancer [5]. However, the underlying mechanisms of

the relationship between different types of diabetes and cancer (especially tumors of the female reproductive system) have not been summarized in detail. This review analyzes this relationship and describes the mechanisms of its occurrence.

Materials and methods. This literature review was carried out with the aim of critically assessing the collected material. The authors performed an electronic search for publications in the PubMed, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, and Scopus databases. The search terms included the words “diabetes mellitus”, “gynecologic cancers”, “ovarian cancer”, “endometrial cancer”, “cervical cancer”, “vaginal cancer” and “vulvar cancer”. The authors independently reviewed those articles whose titles and abstracts were relevant to the search terms. Disagreements between authors regarding eligibility were resolved by consensus. The review included studies published primarily within the last 15 years. Full texts of articles and their abstracts were analyzed.

Epidemiological aspects. The number of people with diabetes continues to increase worldwide, significantly increasing the burden on the healthcare system. According to the latest data, in 2021, the global prevalence of both types of diabetes among adults was 537 million people, and by 2045 it is expected to increase to 783 million people [6]. Diabetes is a fairly common disease among cancer patients, and is a proven risk factor for some solid malignancies, such as pancreatic, liver, colon, kidney, bladder and breast cancer [7]. Epidemiological studies have shown that cancers of the female reproductive system, including endometrial and ovarian (OC) cancer, are more common in people with diabetes. One meta-analysis showed a statistically significant association of T2DM with the risk of endometrial cancer (overall relative risk (RR) 2.10; 95% confidence interval (CI) 1.75–2.53). This meta-analysis also reported an association between T1DM and endometrial cancer (overall RR 3.15; 95% CI 1.07–9.29). In a study by Liu X. et al. provides data demonstrating that patients with T2DM have an increased risk of developing the types of cancer already mentioned above (colon, liver, pancreas, kidney), including endometrial cancer. The authors of the article suggest that the increased risk of developing cancer in patients with diabetes compared to their relatives is associated with various severe metabolic disorders [8]. It should be noted that many studies provide evidence that the incidence of cancer of the ovary, esophagus, endometrium, vulva and vagina, and thyroid gland is higher among women with T1DM.

Pathophysiological conditions and processes leading to the development of oncological diseases in diabetes mellitus

Hyperglycemia. Epidemiological data have shown that hyperglycemia is directly associated with an increased risk of colorectal, liver, gastric, lung and pancreatic cancer [10]. Cells of most types of malignancies predominantly express glucose transporter type 1, which has a high affinity for glucose. It is also worth mentioning the Warburg effect, in which in tumor cells glucose follows the energetically inefficient glycolysis pathway with a high level of lactate production. Increased glycolysis in tumor cells provides the materials necessary for the synthesis of nucleotides, amino acids and lipids [11]. Hyperglycemia stimulates the production of advanced glycation end products (AGEs). AGEs interact with a specific AGE receptor, which leads to activation of the NF- κ B (nuclear factor κ B) signaling pathway and the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in cells, thereby accelerating oxidative stress and leading to the activation of pro-inflammatory signaling pathways [10]. It has been demonstrated that AGEs and activation of downstream pathways promote tumor transformation of epithelial cells [12]. For example, hyperglycemia has been shown to stimulate the proliferation of pancreatic cancer cells through induction of epithelial growth factor (EGF) expression and transactivation of its receptor (EGFR) [13]. EGF and its receptor, in turn, play an important role in the pathogenesis of tumors of the female reproductive system, for example, ovarian cancer and cervical cancer (CC) [14]. In addition, hyperglycemia is responsible for DNA damage, which is the first stage of tumorigenesis [15].

Hyperinsulinemia. In T2DM, insulin resistance leads to the development of compensatory hyperinsulinemia. High concentrations of insulin in the blood play a key role in the pathogenesis of malignant neoplasms, which has been demonstrated in numerous studies both in vitro and in vivo [17]. Using endometrial cancer cell culture, it was found that, on the one hand, hyperinsulinemia leads to a slowdown in the process of mesenchymal-epithelial transition (as a consequence, metastasis and tumor invasion) by inhibiting the expression *COL1A1* (gene encoding the α 1 chain of type I collagen), *IRS2* (insulin receptor substrate-1), however, on the other hand, increases the level of expression *AMFR* (Autocrine Motility Factor Receptor), *FAF1* (FAS-associated factor 1), *MPP3* (Membrane Palmitoylated Protein 3), *PIP2* (phosphatidylinositol 4,5-diphosphate), *VEGFA* (vascular endothelial growth factor), as well as genes of other proteins that promote tumor development and progression [18]. It is assumed that the metabolic effects of insulin, which include the transport of

glucose into the cell, are mediated by activation of the PI3K/Akt signaling pathway, while the mitogenic effect is exerted on cells through Ras/Raf/MAPK (Rat sarcoma virus/RAF protooncogene serine/threonine-protein kinase/MitogenActivated Protein Kinase) signaling pathway, in this pathway the downstream kinases are MEK (Mitogen-Activated Kinase) and ERK (Extracellular signal-Regulated Kinase). Proinsulin and insulin have similar stimulatory effects on MAPK activation, proliferation and migration of breast cancer cells [19]. It is also necessary to note the importance of insulin-like growth factors (IGFs), which are involved in the development of malignant tumors [20].

Obesity. It is widely known that the majority of patients with prediabetes or T2DM are overweight or obese [23]. In obesity, according to the working group of the International Association for the Study of Cancer, there is an increased risk of developing 13 different neoplasms, including endometrial, esophageal, kidney and pancreatic cancer, hepatocellular carcinoma, cancer of the gastric cardia, meningioma; multiple myeloma, colorectal cancer, postmenopausal breast cancer, ovarian, gallbladder and thyroid cancer [24]. An umbrella review of systematic reviews and 204 meta-analyses also found an association between obesity and cancer. This association was especially pronounced for cancer of the gastrointestinal tract and cancer of the female reproductive system [25]. Data from 8 observational studies involving 635,642 patients suggest that bariatric surgery is associated with a reduced risk of all types of cancer (pooled odds ratio (OR) 0.72; 95% CI 0.59–0.87)), as well as obesity-related cancers (pooled OR 0.55; 95% CI 0.31–0.96), including breast cancer (pooled OR 0.50; 95% CI 0.25–0.99) [26].

Inflammation and oxidative stress. Inflammation is one of the key connecting elements between diabetes and cancer. Chronic low-grade inflammation in hypertrophied adipose tissue plays an important role in the pathogenesis of obesity-associated insulin resistance [34]. In turn, chronic inflammation is associated with increased levels of the already mentioned oxidative stress and ROS, which are critical for many processes in cancer development [35]. In addition, due to hyperglycemia, advanced glycation end products and their receptors lead to the development of oxidative stress and increased inflammation, which promotes cell growth, angiogenesis and metastasis [11]. Various studies have identified increased circulating levels of the proinflammatory cytokines IL-1 (interleukin-1), IL-6 (interleukin-6) and TNF- α (tumor necrosis factor-alpha) in patients with diabetes [36]. TNF- α promotes tumor development by activating NF- κ B and increasing the production of ROS

and reactive nitrogen species, which can cause DNA damage. This cytokine also stimulates the growth, proliferation, invasion and metastasis of tumor cells, as well as angiogenesis [37]. Elevated levels of IL-6 have been found in patients with pancreatic cancer, breast cancer, B-cell lymphoma and myeloma [38].

Conclusion. Tumors of the female reproductive system continue to be a serious problem for both patients and the healthcare system. The article provides a literary analysis to assess the influence of chronic hyperglycemia, hyperinsulinemia, systemic inflammation and oxidative stress, as well as changes in the level of sex hormones observed in diabetes on the formation of tumors of the female reproductive system.

References:

1. Отамуродов УГ угли, Абдужамбиллов АН угли, Сабирова ДШ. Гипертиреоз. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(5):134-139.
2. Шухратовна СД, Рустамовна РГ, Нодир Р. Изменения уровня хГ в системе мать-плацента-плод прирезус несовместимой беременности. *Достижения науки и образования*. 2020;(10 (64)):91-93.
3. Хамраев Х, Содиков С, Хамраева Д, Собирова Д. Клинико-функциональное состояние печени у больных с сахарным диабетом. *ЖПБМ*. 2018;(1 (99)):189-191.
4. Даминов АТ, Хакбердиева В, Жаникулов С, Муродхонов С. Клинический случай первичный гипотиреоз. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):131-134.
5. Shukhratovna SD, Suratovich OF. Морфологические особенности коры надпочечников потомства крыс в онтогенезе в условиях внутриутробного воздействия пестицидов через организм матери (обзорная статья). *Journal of biomedicine and practice*. 2023;8(4). Accessed January 12, 2024. <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/biomedicine/article/view/8217>
6. Мизамова МАК, Эшпулатова ГНК, Эшмуродова ЗНК, Салимова ДЭ. Осложнения акромегалии, связанные со здоровьем, текущие и перспективные варианты лечения. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):187-195.
7. Нарбаев А, Джураева З, Курбонова Н, Кувондилов Г, Давранова А, Содиков С. Особенности изучения многофакторного управления сахарным диабетом 2 типа. *Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины*. 2017;(4 (97)):78-79.
8. Ибрагимов УС, Туракулов ЖТУ, Гуломов ШНУ, Салимова ДЭ. Просвещение пациентов: Гипогликемия (низкий уровень глюкозы в крови) у людей с диабетом. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):226-233.
9. Содиков С, Каримова Н, Каримова З. Реабилитация больных пожилого возраста сахарным диабетом 2-типа. *ЖПБМ*. 2017;(4 (97)):105-106.
10. Хамидова МН, Исмадова ИФ, Бердиеров ЖШ, Негматова ГШ, Даминов АТ. Сахарный диабет COVID-19. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*. 2022;2(13):190-204.

11. Шухратовна СД, Кахрамонович ЮУ, Махмудович КТ. Структурные изменения сосудисто-стромального комплекса щитовидной железы при эутиреоидной и токсических формах зоба. *Научный журнал*. 2019;(10 (44)):67-69.
12. Собиржонова КН, Саллохидинович СС, Акбаровна ОМ. Эпидемиологический Статус И Факторы Риска Сахарного Диабета На Сегодняшний День. *MiastoPrzyszłości*. 2023;32:212-219.
13. Salimova DE, Daminov AT. A Clinical case based on the experience of treating hypertension in a patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity and vitamin d deficiency. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2023;2(12):150-154.
14. Takhirovich DA. Assessment of hearing function in individuals with type 2 diabetes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):124-126.
15. Qahramonov FA, Amirov BY, Tursunboyeva LI, Daminov AT. Autoimmuntireoiditbilankasallanganbemorlardagifunksionalbuzilishlarningdifferensialdiagnostikasidaqalqonsimonbezzichliginianiqlash. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3):82-86.
16. Nazira K, Siddikovna TG, Davranovna DA, Takhirovich DA, Tulkinovich OS. Cardiovascular complications in patients who have had covid on the background of diabetes mellitus 2.1. 2021;2(3):37-41.
17. Choriyev S, Gadoeva Z, Mardonova F, Jurakulov F, Hafizov S, Daminov AT. Changes in the thyroid gland in the long period after a new coronavirus infection. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):102-106.
18. Kamalov T, Bahriev N, Yuldashev U, Sabirova D. Clinical and hormonal characteristics of primary hypogonadism in preschool boys. *MedFarm*. 2019;10(9). doi:10.32743/2658-4093.2019.9.10.188
19. Daminov AT, Yuldoshev B, Murodullo I, Naimova N. Clinical case of primary hypothyroidism. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):135-138.
20. Daminov AT, Norkulov A, Turamudov R, Zayniddinova D. Clinical observation of severe itsenko-cushing disease. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):549-556.
21. Daminov A, Khaydarov O, Hasanova M, Abdukakhorova R. Complications of glucocorticoid therapy in patients diabetes survived COVID-19. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*. 2023;3(4):197-200.
22. Takhirovich DA, Corners SJA, Shukhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SG, Zaynuddinovna MG. Course of COVID-19 in patients with diabetes mellitus. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*. 2022;3(02):73-76. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/B6FU2
23. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, Suxrobovna XM, Ikromovna AZ. Diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):381-386.

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24. O'g'li SOS, O'g'li RSO, Taxirovich DA. Diffuz toksik buqoq. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*. 2023;4(1):131-133.
25. Negmatova GS, Toshimova GT qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Effectiveness of correction of dyslipidemia in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 special):269-274.
26. G.Sh N, D.e S, Oybekovma XS, Qamariddinovna XA, O'g'li BJA. Endocrine glands, structure, age features, functions. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):341-345.
27. Sobirjonovna KN. Factors determining the clinical significance of depeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *World Bulletin of Public Health*. 2022;8:67-72.
28. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Family form of nephrogenic x-linked diabetes insuplius. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 special):703-710.
29. Daminov AT, Djabbarova D, Abduvohidova N, Furkatova D, Farxodova S, Ibragimova P. Features of bone tissue remodeling in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(11).
30. Daminov Abdurasul Takhirovich RSU. Features of the clinic, rehabilitation, treatment of autoimmune thyroiditis in the conditions of the iodine-deficiency region. Published online April 12, 2023. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.7820412
31. Shuhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SD. Features of the course of autoimmune hepatitis in children as a variant of autoimmune polyglandular syndrome. *Asia Journ of Multidimensi Resear (AJMR)*. 2020;9(7):89. doi:10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00228.1
32. Erkinovna SD. Features of the Course of Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 with Arterial Hypertension. *Journal NX*. Published online 2020:460-461.
33. Negmatova GS, Xakimova GD qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Features of the rules for insulin injection techniques in elderly and senile patients with diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):259-264.
34. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Features of type 1 diabetes in children who have COVID-19. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):121-123.
35. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Features of vitamin-d metabolism in patients with diabetic nephropathy. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):681-689.
36. Xudoyorov S, Mirkomilova M, Burxonov U, Sayfieva G, Seralieva N, Daminov AT. Fourniers gangrene in modern conditions. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):107-117.
37. Alimovna KN, Sobirjanovna KN, Abdurasul D, Tulkinovich OS. Growth hormone for the treatment of hereditary diseases in children. 10.
38. Negmatova .G.Sh, D.e S, Qizi MZO, Mannobovich MS, Orifjonovich MM. Herpetic meningitis. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):346-348.
39. Ahrorbek N, Myungjae L, Jungjae L, et al. Hormonal Regulation. *Texa Jour of Mutl Stud*. 2023;25:39-43.

40. Ismoilova SI. Impact of vitamin D deficiency on the risk of developing type 1 diabetes. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3).
41. T DA, Umidbekovna UM, Muhitdinovna KN. Methodology of Using Modern Graphics Programs in Teaching Engineering Graphics. *I*. Published online December 8, 2023:158-162.
42. Sabirjanovna KN, Takhirovich DA, Jahongir D, Najmiddin X, Samandar G, Mehrangiz X. Negative Impact of Covid-19 on the Endocrine System. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(8):148-153.
43. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Nevrologiyada endokrin o'zgarishlar. *so'ngi ilmiy tadqiqotlar nazariyasi*. 2023;6(12):417-422.
44. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Pretibial myxedema: pathogenetic features and clinical aspects. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 special):695-702.
45. Negmatova GS, Salimova DE. Qandli diabet 2-tipning arterial gipertenziyabilan birgalikdakechish xususiyatlarivaularnidavolashusullari. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(2):516-519.
46. Taxirovich DA, J T, O E, I A. Qandli diabet-2 tipi bor bemorlarda COVID-19 kasalligini glukokortikoidlar bilan davolash dinamikasini baholash. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*. 2023;34:78-81.
47. G.Sh N, D.e S, Alisherovich BA, Erkin R is the son of S, Bektash U is the son of S. Relationship between diabetic nephropathy and cardiac disorders in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):337-340.
48. Daminov AT, Sa'dullayeva SM qizi, Ismoilova SI qizi. Samarqand viloyatida qandli diabet asoratlari uchrash chastotasi. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 Special):139-142.
49. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, O'g'li IBI, Qizi ADD. The role of gastrointestinal hormones in the pathology of the digestive system. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(6):408-412.
50. Ulugbekovna NP, Bakhtiyorovna RI, Almosovich RA, Takhirovich DA. Thyroid Diseases during Pregnancy and their Impact on Maternal and Fetal Outcomes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(8):188-190.
51. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Time-restricted nutrition as a new strategy for the therapy of obesity and comorbid conditions. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 Special):660-667.
52. Nilufar R, Adkhamjon K. TO The development of cardiovascular diseases effects of environmental factors. *fan, ta'lim, madaniyat va innovatsiya jurnali | Journal of science, education, culture and innovation*. 2022;1(4):100-101.
53. Xoldorov X, Omonov F, Jumayev I, Daminov AT. TYPE 1 Diabetes as a risk factor for bone health in childhood. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*. 2023;2(8):131-135.

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